

On the Immersed and Dry Fatigue of Carbon Fiber/Vinyl Ester Composite Material

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SUMMARY

Experimental results for carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites, that serve as facings for naval sandwich structures, yielded failures under much fewer number of cycles when fatigued under immersed conditions than in air. Failure mechanisms leading to this significant degradation in fatigue behavior of polymeric composites under sea water confinement are discussed.

Keywords: carbon composites, naval applications, sea water degradation, cyclic fatigue

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of sandwich structures in naval craft is of current interest to US and several European navies. Their lightweights lower the center of gravity of the naval vessels, when incorporated in the super structure, and similarly increase the buoyancy of submersibles. The sandwich layup consists of a closed cell polymeric foam layer placed between thin carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester polymeric composite facings. Exposure to sea ambience induces environmental effects into both polymeric facings and polymeric foams. It was established in earlier works that the ingress of sea water is essentially confined to the outer, exposed, facing of the sandwich structure and to just a few adjacent cells of the foam core^{[1],[2]}. Ongoing research by the authors is focused on sea water effects on the mechanical response of both foam and facing individually as well as on the sandwich lay-up. This paper reports the effect of water confinement on the cyclic fatigue behavior of vinyl ester based carbon fiber facing composites.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN PREPERATION

Carbon fiber reinforced/vinyl ester laminated composites consisting of $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ cross-stitched lay-ups are used in this study. Test materials were fabricated at North Carolina A&T University following standard protocol^[3]. Figure 1 shows the dimensions of the specimen as well as the water-filled membrane attached to the central region of the sample. The “wet condition” was achieved by immersing the carbon/vinyl ester samples in a bath of sea water at 40 °C for at least 6 months prior to testing. To simulate the immersed condition the cyclic loading was applied with water container

within the impermeable membrane kept in place until failure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The tension-tension fatigue test of polymer composited was designed based on ASTM D 3479/D 3479 M standards. The cyclic load was applied in a servo-hydraulic test machine at frequency of 1 Hz with an R-ratio ($\sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$) of 0.2 with $\sigma_{\max} = 80$ MPa. All $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimens were subjected to in-plane tensile cyclic loading at 80 percent of ultimate strength. Two to four replicate samples were tested in each of the four following conditions 1) dry samples tested in air, 2) saturated samples tested in air, 3) dry samples tested while immersed in sea water, and 4) saturated samples tested while immersed in sea water.

One inch long tabs and a suitable adhesive were selected in order to minimize tab failures. A four inch long extensometer was used to record strain data, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: carbon fiber vinyl/ester composite specimens

Table 5.2: Typical material properties of carbon fiber vinyl/ester composites

Property	Value	Dimension
Longitudinal modulus $[0/90]_{2s}$	80	GPa
Longitudinal modulus $[\pm 45]_{2s}$	15	GPa
Ultimate strength $[0/90]_{2s}$	450	MPa
Ultimate strength $[\pm 45]_{2s}$	100	MPa

Figure 2: Cyclic set up of tensile fatigue test with a 100 mm extensometer

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Laminated fiber reinforced composite materials exhibit disparate failure mechanisms when fatigued in air or under immersed conditions that lead to earlier failures when submerged in fluid.

This disparity is caused by the fact that damage in the form of microcracks generates capillary paths through which the ambient fluid penetrates the interior of the sample at a rate that is 4 to 5 orders of magnitude faster than its ingress by diffusion. On the other hand, for typical load/unload fatigue frequencies, the time lapse for fluid to traverse across the width of the specimen by capillary motion is several orders of magnitude longer than the duration of a single fatigue cycle.

Consequently, the fluid contained within the capillaries cannot egress the laminate during the unloading stages of fatigue, and remains trapped within them. At those junctures, the near incompressibility of the fluid causes it to exert large pressure inside the capillaries and within other pores, thus increasing the magnitude and extent of internal damage within the laminate and leading to its earlier failure.

For laminates reinforced by straight fibers the dominant failure mechanisms are transverse cracking that, upon reaching characteristic spacings, is followed by inter laminar delaminations. The interplay between those mechanisms is dominated by fracture energy considerations what were shown to be greatly affected by the presence of internal fluids

This was demonstrated in previous studies ^{[4], [5]}, where the water pressure during the down stage of the cyclic loading activated delamination growth, sketched in Figure 3 resulting in the highly distinct failure modes for dry and immersed fatigue, shown in

Figure 4. The disparity in the ensuing fracture mechanisms was quantified by fracture mechanics analyses [5] and explained the accelerated number of cycles to failure recorded under immersed fatigue, shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3: Geometry of delaminated crack assumed in the finite element model.

Figure 4: Observations of transverse cracks in the 90° ply-group delaminations at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces of failed $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3]_s$ gr/ep coupons subjected to fatigue. The peeled-off portion of the 0° ply shown on the top of each photo, indicating extent of delamination. (a) dry and (b) saturated immersed for $\sigma_{\max} = 0.8\sigma_u$. (c) dry and (d) saturated immersed for $\sigma_{\max} = 0.85\sigma_u$. In all cases $R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max} = 0.1$.

Figure 5: Fatigue life diagram for: (a) dry coupons fatigued in air, (b) saturated coupons fatigued in air, and (c) saturated coupons fatigued while immersed in sea water.

In the present case, the across thickness stitching provides an efficient constraint against delamination and, although it does not prevent the capillary ingress of water into the transverse cracks, it minimizes the effect of internal water pressure on the cyclic failure of $[0/90]_{2s}$ samples.

On the other hand, the fatigue response of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ samples is highly sensitive to the internal water pressure that arises during the down loading stages of the cyclic loading. The effect of immersed fatigue can be assessed against the dry case by a comparative order of magnitude analysis for a single edge crack inclined at 45° to the load orientation, as sketched in Figures 6a and 6b below.

Figure 6a: A single edge crack oriented at 45° degrees to the load direction, such as in dry fatigue

Figure 6b: The same crack as in Fig. 6a but with internal pressure p activated during the downloading stage of the fatigue cycle, such as occurs under immersed fatigue.

Since $\sigma_{max} = 80$ MPa, both σ and τ are approximately 40 MPa whereas for $\sigma_{min} = 16$ MPa the aforementioned stresses are about 8 MPa. However due to the near incompressibility of water the resulting value of the internal pressure p is of order of GPa^[4]. This pressure thus dominates the failure scenario.

Experimental results for $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates of carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester composites yielded failures under much fewer numbers of cycles when fatigued under immersed conditions than in air. These are summarized in Figure 7.

The failure mechanisms differed from those observed for straight-fiber reinforcement, since the facing material consisted of cross-ply undulating fiber strands that were tied at their cross-over sites. Although these ties limited the growth of transverse cracks, they still allowed the growth of in-plane cracks under immersed conditions, resulting in more extended damage regions. This contrasted with the localized failure behavior under fatigue in air.

A photo of a representative failed, pre-saturated $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimen fatigued under immersed condition is shown in Figure 8. Note that all immersed samples failed within the central region of the specimen, where the water containing membrane induced capillary action. In contrast, failures of dry and wet specimens fatigued in air were located randomly along the entire gage length of the specimen.

Figure 7: Number of cycles to failure of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ samples under cyclic loading at 1 Hz frequency

Figure 8: Microscopic observation of failed saturated $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ carbon fiber vinyl/ester under immersed fatigue test

Concluding remarks

It was shown in this work that the fatigue life of polymeric composites may be shortened by up to three to six fold when cycling occurs under immersed conditions. Although the current results, which were obtained for samples with exposed edges, may overstate the case - they should still serve as a warning against applying dry fatigue data to immersed circumstances.

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